

Nichiren Buddhism

By Benjamin Dorman, Nanzan University

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Nichiren Buddhism, named after the 13th-century Japanese Buddhist priest Nichiren 日蓮 (1222–1282), is a tradition that began as one of the new Buddhist movements of the Kamakura period (1185–1333). Its teachings are based on close to 500 extant doctrinal essays and letters to his followers, either written by or attributed to Nichiren by his later disciples. Nichiren maintained that faith in the Lotus Sutra alone was the only way that people could attain enlightenment during "mappō" (the Final Dharma age). This was a period of social unrest in Japan, characterized by internal strife, foreign invasion by the Mongols (twice in Nichiren's lifetime), pestilence, famine, and natural disasters. Nichiren interpreted the circumstances of the age to be a result of the people's adherence to incorrect teachings. He remonstrated with the authorities and wrote treatises expounding his belief in the salvific power of the Lotus Sutra alone in the age. His exclusive stance led to conflict with the authorities in Kamakura, and he was twice exiled. His followers were also imprisoned, had their lands seized, or were executed. Nevertheless, his community eventually grew into a major Buddhist tradition. Nichiren promoted the practice of chanting the formula *Namu-myōhō-renge-kyō* 南無妙法蓮華經, the sutra's "daimoku" 題目 or title. He stated that the entirety of all Buddhist truth was contained in the "Daimoku" and that repetition of the phrase enabled the realization of Buddhahood. He inscribed the "honzon" 本尊 (or the honorific "Gohonzon" ご本尊), the object of worship in Nichiren temples and also in lay believer's homes. This is a graphic representation of the daimoku down the center surrounded by various deities that appear in the sutra. The core scriptures of all Nichiren groups are the Lotus Sutra and Nichiren's writings ("goshō" 御書). While all groups adhere to these teaching in various forms, *Risshō Kōsei Kai* and *Reiyūkai* also incorporate beliefs and practices of ancestor veneration. After Nichiren's death, the school split into various groups, the most notable being *Nichiren Shū* and *Nichiren Shōshū*, which achieved phenomenal growth due to the lay membership of the *Soka Gakkai* (until 1992). There are close to forty religious groups that claim descent from Nichiren, including traditional Buddhist temple groups associated with *Nichiren Shōshū* and various *Nichiren Shū* schools, and modern lay organizations, such as *Soka Gakkai*, *Risshō Kōsei Kai*, *Reiyūkai*, *Kenshokai*, *Shoshinkai*, and *Honmon Butsurū-shū*. The core scriptures of all Nichiren groups are the Lotus Sutra and Nichiren's writings ("goshō" 御書). Views of Nichiren have varied widely. Some have considered him to be harsh and uncompromising, even arrogant, while others viewed him as a compassionate and gentle teacher. While both Japanese and Western Nichiren scholarship did present him and the tradition as exclusive, self-righteous, and intolerant, recently these views have been questioned. The two methods of teaching the Dharma, "shōjū" 摂受 ("to embrace and accept") and "shakubuku" 折伏 ("to break and subdue"), which are found in Buddhist canonical sources, and their application at various times by adherents no doubt contributed to this. Nichiren wrote about both methods, and while he believed that "shakubuku" was most suited for the Final Dharma age, he acknowledged that shōjū could be appropriate depending upon the place and the people. Some wartime Nichirenist movements promoted extreme ultranationalism. *Soka Gakkai*, which achieved remarkable growth from the 1950s with the "great march of shakubuku" under its Second President, Tōda Josei, developed a reputation for aggressive proselytization. *Soka Gakkai* was affiliated with *Nichiren Shōshū* until 1991, when it was excommunicated by the sect. *Soka Gakkai* is the most prominent of all Nichiren groups, and *Soka Gakkai International (SGI)* states that it has members in 192 countries.

Date Range: 1222 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nichiren Buddhism

Region tags: Asia, Europe, Middle East, Transnational, International, Global, Oceania, Africa, South America, Japan, Latin America and the Caribbean, North America

This map reflects the global of the Soka Gakkai, a lay organization that adheres to a form of Nichiren Buddhism. According to its official website, it has members in 192 countries and territories and ninety registered constituent organizations.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Habito, Ruben L. F., and Jacqueline I. Stone, guest editors (1999). "Revisiting Nichiren." Special Issue. "Japanese Journal of Religious Studies," vol. 26 3/4.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.nichirensoshu.or.jp/eng/index.html>

– Source 1 Description: Nichiren Shōshū webpage. Contains information on Nichiren and his teachings, the head temple Taisekiji, the practice, and links to temples in Japan and overseas (only in Japanese)

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.nichiren.or.jp/english/>

– Source 2 Description: Nichirensū Portal. Contains general information about Buddhism, Shakyamuni, and Nichiren, with more specific information on Nichiren's teachings. Also contains links on temples in Japan and overseas (the latter contains links to temples in Hawaii, North America, South America, Europe, and Asia)

– Source 3 URL: <https://www.sokaglobal.org/>

– Source 3 Description: Soka Gakkai Global. Information about overseas branches, essentials of the practice, articles and faith testimonials, and links to sites on the first three presidents of the Soka Gakkai.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.nichirenlibrary.org/>

– Source 1 Description: Soka Gakkai's Nichiren Buddhism Library

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Nichiren's insistence on the Lotus Sutra as the only practice for the Final Dharma age brought him and his followers in direct conflict with the authorities and other religious sects. Nichiren was attacked on occasion and exiled; his followers were persecuted and some were executed. In the post-WWII period, Soka Gakkai directly challenged other religious groups, although it took a more accommodating stance in the 1960s.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: Nichiren Shū is often considered one of the more open and accommodating branches of Nichiren Buddhism. Nichiren Shōshū maintains a strict adherence to what it considers the orthodox teachings of Nichiren. It generally does not engage in interfaith activities and often presents its teachings as the only correct interpretation of Nichiren Buddhism. While these days Soka Gakkai is accommodating/pluralistic toward other religious groups, when Nichiren Shōshū excommunicated Soka Gakkai and its senior leaders in November 1991, citing doctrinal deviations, one of the reasons cited was the Soka Gakkai's defiant staging of concerts featuring Beethoven's Ode to Joy, with its Christian themes, was incongruent with Nichiren Shōshū doctrine. Risshō Kōseikai is generally seen as accommodating and pluralistic. It actively engages in interfaith dialogue and cooperation.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– I don't know

Notes: This depends on factors like the context, power dynamics, historical background, and attitudes. How proselytization efforts are viewed, for example, may have an impact on this.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Nichiren Shū and Nichiren Shōshū participate in Gojukai, a formal ceremony in which a person receives the Gohonzon, a sacred mandala central to Nichiren Buddhism. The Soka Gakkai has a Gohonzon conferral ceremony. Those joining Risshō Kōseikai receive a Honzon (called "Daigohonzon"), a scroll with an image of Shakyamuni Buddha.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: In Nichiren Buddhist groups, the approach to proselytizing varies between different organizations.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

Notes: While not mandated as an obligation, in Soka Gakkai members are actively encouraged to proselytize. Of all groups, it is probably the most active in this regard.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Notes: This depends on the perspective. Although it has changed its approach, Soka Gakkai was known for its rather aggressive proselytization activities in Japan. This image, although not accurate these days, still persists in Japan to a certain extent.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: Under article 20 of the Japanese constitution, "No religious organization shall receive any privileges from the State, nor exercise any political authority." The extent to which any religious group receives "support" from a politician or politicians within the ruling party is quite a grey area in Japanese politics.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 10356030

Notes: In Japan, Soka Gakkai claims a total of 8.27 million member households and 2.8 million members outside Japan. For Risshō Kōseikai, some estimates suggest around 2.72 million adherents, primarily in Japan. Accurately quantifying the number of adherents in religious groups can be challenging due to how membership is defined, changes over time, and the availability of data. Numbers can fluctuate depending on the group's own reporting as well. It must be stated, however, that Statistics from the Japanese Agency for Cultural Affairs tabled in 2023 listed the total number of adherents in "Nichiren-related groups" as 10356030.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (intolerant of other affiliations)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– No

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Yes

Notes: This is the case for Soka Gakkai. I do not know the case of other groups.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Notes: Not in the case of Soka Gakkai, although Soka Gakkai has claimed since 1992 that Nichiren Shōshū required this obedient and unquestioned acceptance of the high priest's pronouncements.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Central to all groups is the Lotus Sutra and Nichiren's writings (Gosho). Risshō Kōseikai studies books and teachers of its founders. Reiyūkai, which also incorporates ancestor worship, sometimes includes related texts. Soka Gakkai includes other texts, such as Ikeda Daisaku's "The Human Revolution" and "The New Human Revolution" in terms of the group's history and spiritual focus. Risshō Kōseikai and Reiyūkai also have various materials and texts that include guidelines and teachings on ancestor veneration.

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: The Lotus Sutra is believed to be the teachings of Shakyamuni Buddha.

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: In the case with Soka Gakkai, the first three presidents (Makiguchi Tsunesaburo, Toda Josei, and Ikeda Daisaku) are viewed as exceptional, but non-divine, human beings.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– No

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– Yes

Notes: This is the case with Nichiren Shōshū.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Nichiren Shū, Nichiren Shōshū, Soka Gakkai, Risshō Kōseikai, and Reiyūkai, there are specific individuals or groups of people who are trained in transmitting the scriptures associated with their particular traditions. Nichiren Shū priests and monks study the Lotus Sutra, Nichiren's writings, and additional doctrinal texts at seminaries and through apprenticeships under senior priests. Nichiren Shōshū maintains a strict clerical hierarchy, and its priests undergo rigorous training in the sect's doctrines, particularly those writings deemed orthodox within their tradition. While Soka Gakkai does not have a priesthood, it has a well-organized leadership structure where leaders at various levels who facilitate study groups, lead discussions, and provide guidance to members on practicing and understanding the teachings. Soka Gakkai encourages the "three pillars" of "faith, practice, and study" amongst the membership, and runs various study programs and examinations on Nichiren's writings and Soka Gakkai history. Risshō Kōseikai trains lay leaders and Dharma teachers who are educated in the teachings of the Lotus Sutra and Nichiren's principles as interpreted by the organization. They lead study sessions at local branches and during community gatherings. In Reiyūkai more experienced members train newer ones in the teachings and practices, particularly those related to ancestor veneration and the application of Buddhist principles in daily life.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Notes: There is no codified canon of scriptures among Nichiren groups. However, common to all

groups is the central scripture of The Lotus Sutra (Saddharma Puṇḍarīka Sūtra) and Nichiren's writings (Gosho). Interpretations of these vary depending on the group.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– No

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Notes: Many Nichiren temples have cemeteries. Soka Gakkai owns a number of cemeteries in Japan.

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– I don't know

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: The Gohonzon is the primary object of veneration in Nichiren Buddhism. It is a calligraphic mandala inscribed on paper or wood, containing Chinese and Sanskrit characters. The characters inscribed include the name of the Lotus Sutra's title, "Namu-myoho-renge-kyo," along with names of deities and historical and mythological figures who represent various Buddhist virtues and principles. Reiyūkai includes ancestral tablets, which serve as a physical representation to honor deceased family members during Buddhist rituals.

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

Notes: Gohonzon are present in temples, cultural centers, and halls.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

Notes: Risshō Kōseikai temples and worship halls features statues of Shakyamuni Buddha.

- ↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):
 - No
- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife:
 - No
- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):
 - No
- ↳ Humans:
 - No
- ↳ Other features of iconography:
 - I don't know

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: The head temple of Nichiren Shōshū, Taisekiji. Soka Gakkai built the "Hall of the Great Vow for Kosen-rufu" in 2018.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.
Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: In Nichiren Buddhism, the concept of Nine Consciousness is as follows: - The five senses. - The sixth consciousness, where sensory input is integrated. - The seventh consciousness, which is inner thought not connected to sensory input. One can distinguish oneself from others. This is similar to the concept of ego. - The eighth consciousness (Sanskrit: “alaya” or “storehouse consciousness”). One’s karmic energy through interactions with others, and the causes and effects accumulated over one’s lifetime are stored. This consciousness, unlike the previous seven, continues after death. Karma is not static and can change, depending on the causes one makes. - The ninth consciousness is the Buddha nature (Sanskrit: “amala” consciousness), expressed as “namu- myōhō- renge-kyō, the phrase chanted by all Nichiren Buddhists. This is considered to be the ultimate law of the universe. Through connecting with this consciousness, humans can manifest Buddha wisdom or attain enlightenment.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– I don't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form:

– Yes

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Yes

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– Yes [specify]: Buddhism posits that it is possible to be reborn into various forms that go beyond human and animal categories. These forms—be they heavenly, ghostly, or hellish—are all considered within the cycle of birth, death, and rebirth driven by karma. Nichiren mentions different forms, such as asuras and hungry ghosts, in his writings.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: In Japan, almost all deceased are cremated and ashes are placed in cemeteries. But the situation may differ overseas, particularly with Soka Gakkai International adherents who may have family members or traditions requiring different methods of burial. The organization does not have a formal policy on this issue.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: This is sometimes the case in Japan.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– I don't know

↳ Other formal burial type:

– I don't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Nichiren used ideas from the Tendai (Ch: Tiantai) tradition of "ten worlds," which forms the foundation of the view of life. These are (1) the world of hell, (2) the world of hungry spirits, (3) the world of animals, (4) the world of asuras, (5) the world of human beings, (6) the world of heavenly beings, (7) the world of voice-hearers, (8) the world of cause-awakened ones, (9) the world of bodhisattvas, and (10) the world of buddhas. While there are different names for these worlds, a common rendering is as follows: 1) hell, 2) hunger, 3) animality, 4) anger, 5) humanity, 6) heaven, 7) learning, 8) realization, 9) bodhisattvas, and 10) Buddhahood. The first six are the six paths, the last four are the four noble worlds. The six paths is the cycle of birth, mundane existence, and death (in Sanskrit, this is Saṃsāra), perpetuated by desire, ignorance, and karma. The four noble worlds are the higher realms that eventually lead to Buddhahood. It is important to note that these are not distinct and separate worlds in teachings of the Lotus Sutra. Living beings of the nine worlds from hell to bodhisattva possess the world of buddhas, just as buddhas possess the other nine worlds. This is called the mutual possession of the Ten Worlds. In Nichiren's mandala, the Gohonzon, all these worlds and beings are graphically represented, with the words "Namu-myōhō-enge-kyō" (Buddhahood) written down the center. Although Nichirenist doctrine includes reference to what appear to be supernatural beings, in terms of daily life, these are often described as functions of the universe and in human beings that operate in daily life. While there are references to various realms of existence and types of beings, including spirits, these are not so much literal beings that one might see or be felt, but are generally understood metaphorically or as aspects of the mind and experience. Although the NRMs Reiyūkai and Risshō Kōseikai are distinguished from other Nichiren groups in that they believe in the influence and presence of ancestors and potentially other spiritual beings, this is generally conceptualized as a spiritual or metaphysical presence rather than physical sightings of spirits or direct communication.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: See broader explanation above.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– I don't know

Notes: See broader explanation above, particularly in relation to the NRMs Reiyūkai and Risshō Kōseikai.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– I don't know

Notes: See broader explanation above, particularly in relation to the NRMs Reiyūkai and Risshō Kōseikai.

- ↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:
– I don't know
Notes: See broader explanation above, particularly in relation to the NRMs Reiyūkai and Risshō Kōseikai.
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– I don't know
Notes: In the NRMs Reiyūkai and Risshō Kōseikai, there is a belief in the indirect causal spiritual efficacy of ancestors in this world, and this is manifested through the practices of ancestor veneration and memorial rituals. The influence of ancestors is generally perceived as indirect and operates through spiritual, karmic, or moral channels rather than through direct physical intervention.
- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
– I don't know
Notes: Within the practice of ancestor veneration, as practiced by the NRMs Reiyūkai and Risshō Kōseikai, human spirits retain some form of memory or consciousness of their earthly life.
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
– I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
– I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits possess hunger:
– I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:
– I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
– I don't know
Notes: See broader response about, in relation to Reiyūkai and Risshō Kōseikai and ancestor veneration.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– I don't know

Notes: See the previous answer to the question "Are supernatural beings present?"

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– I don't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

Notes: While this is generally true, the organization of Risshō Kōseikai and Reiyūkai somewhat resemble a kinship or family model because they emphasize ancestor veneration as a core part of its practice.

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– No

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– I don't know

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– I don't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Nichiren Buddhist groups, including Nichiren Shū and Nichiren Shōshū, as well as newer lay movements like Soka Gakkai, Reiyūkai, and Risshō Kōseikai, often prescribe and reinforce certain social norms and ethical behaviors through their teachings and community practices.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Nichiren Buddhist groups can emphasize moral norms derived from Buddhist principles, which sometimes challenge or supplement conventional social norms depending on the cultural and social context.

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– I don't know

Notes: It is difficult to state to what extent this exists because there are a number of different Nichiren Buddhist groups. But they can emphasize moral norms derived from Buddhist principles, which sometimes challenge or supplement conventional social norms depending on the cultural and social context.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals within society

Notes: Moral norms include compassion and altruism, integrity and honesty, justice and peace, and respect for life. Many Nichiren groups, including Risshō Kōsekai and Soka Gakkai, are actively involved in peace-building and social justice efforts, reflecting their moral stance on the importance of peace and equity.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

- ↳ Generosity / charity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - Yes
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:
 - Yes
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - Yes
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
 - Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):
– Yes

↳ Power / status / nobility:
– Yes

↳ Humility / modesty:
– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
– Yes

↳ Optimism / hope:
– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:
– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:
– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– I don't know

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– I don't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: While the level of commitment is up to the individual, most new religious movements (such as Soka Gakkai, Reiyūkai, and Risshō Kōseikai) hold meetings, conduct individual and communal prayers, and attend conferences or other events associated with the group. There are also lay groups associated with Nichiren Shū and Nichiren Shōshū temples that hold various meetings and services. The priesthood of Nichiren Shū and Nichiren Shōshu also hold regular meetings, services, and prayers.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Notes: This varies from individual to individual, household to household.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: As far as I know, this is not "required" but optional. I would say "encourage participation in large scale rituals" would be more accurate.

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is dependent on the location (country, region), and the organization.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Again, this is dependent on the location (country, region), and the organization.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Several groups have split from Nichiren Shōshū due to doctrinal disputes and other conflicts. These include Kenshōkai (now Fuji Taiseki-ji Kenshōkai), Shōshinkai, and Soka Gakkai. There have been cases within Soka Gakkai where leaders have been removed from their positions e to promoting unorthodox doctrines. Nichiren Shū has also seen groups form due to doctrinal and other issues, such as Kempon Hokke and Honmon Butsuryū-shū. Soka Gakkai, Reiyūkai, and Risshō Kōseikai have mechanisms to ensure adherence to their specific teachings and practices. These include leadership training sessions, leadership guidance, regular meetings, and publications that are used for doctrinal training.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: For traditional sects like Nichiren Shū and Nichiren Shōshū, as well as modern lay movements such as Soka Gakkai, Reiyūkai, and Risshō Kōseikai, hold various educational

programs, regular group rituals, and systems of leadership and community support that together ensure the continuity and correctness of practice across the community. The sects hold regular rituals and ceremonies, training for priests and lay leaders, and guidance from priests. The lay movements hold small group meetings, training/education programs, different kinds of monitoring by leaders, and produce publications that discuss orthodox practice.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:
– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:
– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The societies are pluralistic, secular, technologically advanced, and diverse. Also, Nichiren groups are global.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: Japanese Buddhist NGOs, such as the Buddhist NGO Network of Japan (BNN), which includes members affiliated with Nichiren temple groups, and the Buddhist Aid Center (BAC), whose members include Nichiren Shū priests, are organizations that work to support international organizations that provide famine relief (or, more broadly, disaster relief. In the Japanese context, NGO refers specifically to a group engaged in international cooperation activities and not directly focused on domestic issues within Japan. In the case of Soka Gakkai, institutionalized famine relief occurs through Soka Gakkai International's (SGI) affiliation with the United Nations as an NGO. Risshō Kōseikai runs a "Donate-A-Meal" movement in which participants skips some meals over a month and the money saved is used for emergency relief and development aid projects around the world, including the UN World Food Programme (WFP). Reiyūkai also occasionally contributes to broader relief efforts as part of a coalition

or through contributions to more specialized organizations, although these activities are on a smaller scale as those of the SGI or Risshō Kōseikai. These groups do not typically operate as primary providers of famine relief, they do contribute to these efforts through institutional support, fundraising, and by mobilizing their extensive member networks to assist in global humanitarian initiatives.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: Japanese Buddhist NGOs, such as the Buddhist NGO Network of Japan (BNN), which includes members affiliated with Nichiren temple groups, and the Buddhist Aid Center (BAC), whose members include Nichiren Shū priests, are organizations that work to support international organizations that provide poverty relief (or, more broadly, disaster relief. In the Japanese context, NGO refers specifically to a group engaged in international cooperation activities and not directly focused on domestic issues within Japan. In the case of Soka Gakkai, institutionalized famine relief occurs through Soka Gakkai International's (SGI) affiliation with the United Nations as an NGO. Risshō Kōseikai and Reiyūkai are also involved with poverty relief through their involvement with organizations engaged in international poverty relief. These groups do not typically operate as primary providers of poverty relief, they do contribute to these efforts through institutional support, fundraising, and by mobilizing their extensive member networks to assist in global humanitarian initiatives.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: Risshō Kōseikai operates residential care facilities and supports existing facilities for the elderly and infirm.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: **Nichiren Shū** While Nichiren Shū has a decentralized structure, with each temple enjoying a considerable degree of autonomy, there is still a formal bureaucratic structure at the higher levels, which includes a head temple (Minobusan Kuonji) and administrative bodies. Lay members typically interact with this bureaucracy through their local temples and priests, who act as intermediaries. **Nichiren Shōshū** Nichiren Shōshū has a more centralized structure, with the head temple, Taisekiji, playing a pivotal role in all major doctrinal and administrative decisions. It maintains a strict hierarchy, and the priesthood has significant control over religious practices and the interpretation of doctrine. Lay believers, known as Hokkeko members, typically interact with the sect's bureaucracy through their local temples and the priests assigned to them. **Soka Gakkai** Soka Gakkai has a very structured and extensive bureaucratic system, especially given its size and international presence. Members often interact with a multi-layered bureaucracy that includes local, regional, national, and international leadership levels. **Rissho Koseikai** and **Reiyukai** Rissho Koseikai and Reiyukai, similar to Soka Gakkai, have structured organizational hierarchies. Members interact with the bureaucracy through participation in study sessions, community service activities, and organizational meetings.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents of Nichiren groups, particularly those with extensive social programs like Soka Gakkai and Rissho Koseikai, interact with government bodies and regulatory agencies. These interactions are necessary for compliance with local and national laws, particularly in areas like nonprofit operations, charitable activities, and international operations. Nichiren groups often have strong educational components, and adherents interact with educational institutions both in Japan and internationally through academic collaborations and public education initiatives. Some groups, including Soka Gakkai and Risshō Kōseikai, engage in interfaith dialogue and participate in ecumenical organizations to promote mutual understanding and cooperation among different faith communities. This also includes collaborating with other religious organizations on community service projects that address common societal issues like poverty, disaster relief, and environmental conservation. Risshō Kōseikai interacts with health care institutions, especially in activities related to health care, elderly care, and

hospice services. Soka Gakkai has significant interactions with media organizations within Japan and overseas to promote their activities, beliefs, and responses to societal issues.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Notes: Nichiren groups provide transportation infrastructure when it involves training or educational courses for adherents, or visiting temples.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: This would depend on the size of the group, and the activity in question. For example, when Nichiren Shōshū holds events at the head temple, Taisekiji, private bus companies and trains are used to transport participants.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: Nichiren groups do not levy taxes as they are religious organizations and not governmental entities. They also do not levy tithes, or mandatory monetary contributions. However, they do encourage voluntary donations and membership contributions. Adherents are generally encouraged to contribute according to their financial ability and personal commitment to the organization's goals.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents, like all citizens or residents, are subject to the general tax laws of the country or region in which they reside.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Local police forces and other state-provided services

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Like other citizens, they must interact with local and national judicial systems.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: While they do not enforce institutionalized punishment in the way that a state or governmental authority might, depending on the group there are various consequences for those who do not adhere to, or go against, internal regulations and guidelines that adherents are expected to follow.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents of various Nichiren groups, like all individuals, are subject to the laws and regulations of the countries in which they reside. If they commit a civil or criminal offence, they are accountable to the legal systems outside their religious organizations.

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: In the case of Japan.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– I don't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– I don't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an

institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: While this is the case in general, in case of disaster, institutions other than the group in question may provide food.

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